

Factors that Influence Quality of Life Male Prisoners: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: Male prisoners are faced with a variety of unexpected situations and conditions while in correctional institutions. The sudden change experienced by prisoners has an impact on the Quality of Life (QoL) they have. However, research that addresses these factors systematically is not yet available. Therefore, this study wants to see what factors influence prisoners QoL while in prison. Method: This literature review uses a variety of articles and books obtained through ScienceDirect, EBSCO and PubMed health, published from January 2004 to September 2019, using the quality of the keywords of life, inmates, and male prison. Results: The literature states that the factors that influence QoL for male WBP include internal factors (loss of freedom, inappropriate living standards, changes in status and roles) and external factors (prison conditions, length of the detention period, and lack of family interaction). Conclusion: The knowledge of community nurses about the many factors that influence male QBL can make it easier to identify problems and provide nursing actions.

KEYWORDS: Inmates; Male prisoners; Quality of life

INTRODUCTION

The number of correctional prisoners (WBP) was identified to exceed the threshold of occupancy while in correctional institutions.¹ Recorded the number of Indonesian prisoners in one of the prisons has doubled from the normal capacity of 663 WBP to 1144 WBP in 2018, 1390 WBP in 2019, and 1362 WBP in February 2020.² Over capacity or overload increased problems faced by inmates.³ A preliminary study in a Central Java Lapas states that human resources (HR) at prison not balanced with the number of prisoners resulted in problem handling being not optimal so there is an inability to identify factors in depth related to changes that occur in prisoners quality of life (QoL). Life changes that are not in line with expectations occur in prisoners also have an impact on QoL.^{3,4} The decrease in QoL level indicates the inability of prisoners to adapt and the low ability to control positive emotions. Research reveals that several factors influence prisoners QoL. Haney (2001) and Liebling (2008) revealed that prison conditions that differ from previous living environments affect the way prisoners adapts. Bakker, Morris, & Janus (1978) and Bruce & Larweh (2017) state that policies in prison limit the freedom of prisoners so that they cannot express themselves optimally.^{9,10} Prisoners problems also occur along with changes in status and roles that occur when receiving a decision to inhabit prisons.^{11,12} Lack of interaction with family both directly and indirectly and the length of detention obtained can reduce the positive emotions possessed by the prisoners so that the impact on the QoL owned.^{13,14} Lapas becomes a new environment where prisoners are demanded to be able to accept every situation condition that occurs.^{15,16} The problems faced by prisoners are caused by various factors that arise internally and externally. Community nurses are responsible for being able to identify the main causes of problems in QoL so that they can make promotive and preventive efforts to maintain the mental health of prisoners. However, as yet no literature systematically discusses the factors that influence prisoners QoL so this research is important to do.

METHODOLOGY

This literature review uses 12 articles and 3 books obtained through ScienceDirect, EBSCO and PubMed health, published from January 2004 to September 2019, using the quality of the keywords of life, inmates, and male prison

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Factors that Influence Prisoners QoL

Factors that Influence Prisoners QoL	Internal factors
	1. Loss of freedom
	2. Unsuitable living standard
	3. Changes in status and roles
	External factors
	1. Prison Conditions
2. Length of detention	
	3. Lack of family interaction

The results obtained from the literature states that the factors that influence the QoL of prisoners are divided into internal factors and external factors.

1. Internal factor

Legal decisions regarding criminal acts make the prisoners must stay in prison. ¹⁷ The loss of freedom is interpreted as an impact of the limitations of the prisoners in conducting activities in the outside world. ¹⁸ Prisoners who are unable to maintain adaptive coping mechanisms in dealing with the loss of the right to freedom to do something will affect the QoL owned. ¹⁹ Prisoners perceived changes in living standards related to mismatches between hopes and ideals regarding a decent life to the reality that requires prisoners to stay in prison. ^{20,21} Acceptance that prisoners is unable to maintain on changes can increase feelings of stress, anxiety, to stress which ultimately affects QoL. ^{22,23}

Every individual has the status and role that must be done to meet the needs of life. ²⁴ The application of the status and role of the prisoners who are in prison cannot be carried out properly because of the limitations of freedom. ²⁵ Feelings of inadequacy experienced by the prisoners relating to the application of self-function can lead to behavior inferiority.

2. External factor

Changes in environmental conditions occupied by prisoners can be a factor that influences the level of QoL. ²⁶ Prisoners are required to be able to adapt to prisons which certainly have different levels of comfort and security when compared to when prisoners was in a family environment. ⁸ Prisoners who are unable to accept conditions Prisons can quickly affect positive thinking patterns and reduce the level of QoL they have. ¹⁹

The length of detention and lack of family interaction can affect the prisoners QoL. ¹³ Research suggests that the prisoners QoL who meets with the family directly will be different from the prisoners who only makes indirect contact. ²⁷ Being away from the family for a long period can cause an increasing dissatisfaction with life that occurs due to the lack of implementation of family functions and roles. ⁴

CONCLUSION

Prisoners QoL in prison is influenced by two main factors namely internal and external. Community nurse have the responsibility by making preventive and promotive efforts to maintain prisoners QoL. Knowledge of the factors that influence prisoners QoL is needed to facilitate the identification of problems and determine appropriate actions by the problems that occur.

REFERENCES

1. Sistem Database Pemasarakatan. Laporan penghuni lapas. 2019.
2. Sistem Database Pemasarakatan. Data penghuni Lapas kelas I Semarang. 2019.
3. WHO. WHOQOL-BREF introduction, administration, scoring, and generic version of the assessment. 1996;(December).
4. Ventegodt S, Merrick J, Andersen NJ. Quality of life theory II. Quality of life as the realization of life potential: A biological theory of human being. Sci World J [Internet]. 2003;3:1041–9. Available from: <http://www.hindawi.com/journals/tswj/2003/241024/abs/>
5. Liebling A. Incentives and earned privileges revisited: Fairness, discretion, and the quality of prison life. J Scand Stud

- Criminol Crime Prev. 2008;25–42.
6. Haney C. The psychological impact of incarceration: Implications for post-prison adjustment. Univ California, St Cruz. 2001;(December 2001):19.
 7. Bakker LJ, Morris BA, Janus LM. Hidden victims of crime. Soc Work. 1978;23:143–8.
 8. Bruce D, Larweh E. Self-esteem, needs satisfaction and psychological well-being of inmates at James Camp Prison in Ghana. Int J Humanit Soc Sci Educ. 2017;4(9):32–9.
 9. Tomar S. The psychological effects of incarceration on inmates. Vol. 16, Delhi Psychiatry Journal. 2013. p. 66–72.
 10. Parse RR. The lived experience of suffering: A Parse research method study. Nurs Sci Q [Internet]. 2001;14(4):330–8. Available from: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/18544785>
 11. Richards B. The experience of long-term imprisonment: An exploratory investigation. British J Criminol. 1978;18(2):162–9.
 12. Liebling A, Maruna S. The effects of imprisonment. New York: Institute of Criminology, University of Cambridge; 2005.
 13. Niewiadomska I, Fel S. The importance of family support in the process of the adjustment of current and former prisoners. Pers Challenges. 2015;5(2):165–79.
 14. Toussaint L, Sirois F, Hirsch J, Weber A, Vajda C, Schelling J, et al. Gratitude mediates quality of life differences between fibromyalgia patients and healthy controls. Qual Life Res. 2017;
 15. Yi Y, Turney K, Wildeman C. Mental health among jail and prison inmates. Am J Mens Health. 2017;11(4):900–9.
 16. O'Connor TP, Duncan JB. The sociology of humanist, spiritual, and religious practice in prison: Supporting responsivity and desistance from crime. Religions. 2011;2(4):590–610.
 17. UU RI. UU Republik Indonesia no 12 tahun 1995 tentang pemyarakatan [Internet]. 1995. Available from: www.bphn.go.id
 18. Hughes RC. Imprisonment and the right to freedom of movement. Rethink Punishm Era Mass Incarcer. 2017;89–104.
 19. Kalonji MPG, Ngongo LO, Ilunga FI, Albert A, Giet D. Quality of life perception by inmates in the central prison of Mbuji-Mayi, Democratic Republic of Congo. Int J Med Res Heal Sci. 2017;6(12):42–8.
 20. Profile SEE. Coping with stress and the sense of quality of life in inmates of correctional facilities Coping with stress and the sense of quality of life in inmates of correctional facilities. 2018;(August).
 21. Park À. The quality of prison life at the Ledoners Penitentiary system: A comparative analysis. 2018;
 22. Kelly JD. Your best life: Breaking the cycle: the power of gratitude. Clin Orthop Relat Res. 2016;
 23. Schalock RL. The concept of quality of life: What we know and do not know. J Intellect Disabil Res. 2004;48(3):203–16.
 24. Aflakseir A. The role of social support and coping strategies on mental health of a group of Iranian disabled war veterans. Iran J Psychiatry [Internet]. 2010;5(3):102–7. Available from: <http://ovidsp.ovid.com/ovidweb.cgi?T=JS&PAGE=reference&D=prem&NEWS=N&AN=22952501>
 25. Abramowitz MJ. Freedom in The World 2018: Democracy in Crisis. Free House. 2018;1–24.
 26. Maruca AT, Shelton D. Correctional Nursing Interventions for Incarcerated Persons with Mental Disorders: An Integrative Review. Issues Ment Health Nurs. 2016;37(5):285–92.
 27. Millar MG. The effects of direct and indirect experience on affective and cognitive responses and the attitude-behavior relation. J Exp Soc Psychol. 1996;579(32):561–79.